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Deliverable

D4.8 Exploitation and Dissemination Plan (1)

Work package 4

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PU	Public	X
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

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Version history

2023-06-21 V1-1 Initial Version, Katja Bierau

Definitions

TGs - target groups

IP - intellectual property

KOs - Knowledge Outputs

ILEA - league against epilepsy

MDR - medical device reporting

QMS - Quality Management System

UDI - unique identifier

ILAE - international league against epilepsy

CA - consortium agreement

GDPR - General Data Protection Regulation

IPR - intellectual property rights

IRB - Institutional Review Boards

Overview Exploitation Plan

This plan will be developed for individual or clusters of knowledge outputs (KOs) depending on their type, intellectual property (IP) conditions, and target groups (TGs) or end-user target audiences. AKA will identify the most suitable channels and means for transferring the outputs to our TGs, which will ensure tailor-made transfer based on end-user focus. Additionally, we will ensure that the exploitation strategies are aligned with the regulatory and ethical considerations surrounding the use of neurotechnology. The device developed in AEGEUS will provide an innovative way to aid scientific functional brain imaging and clinical diagnostics. The long-term vision is that the functions of xxx will be further developed and tested as a clinical intervention, expanding therapeutic options for neurological and psychiatric patients. This long-term vision includes a closed-loop functionality for diagnosis and treatment.

The neuroimaging business is quite impressive in size, being able to make 3 billion euros in revenues worldwide annually, out of the total of €22.5 billion of global yearly biomedical imaging revenues. These numbers provide scope and a basis for expanding into this market. In fact, the AEGEUS partnership includes substantial expertise in start-ups and spin-offs both from the academic incubation side (FHG) and from the industrial side (GTEC). Within the present project, we will develop a prototype that is ready to be taken to the next stage of exploitation in a future project. Future exploitable KOs could therefore focus on a) submission of data for medical device agencies and to acquire CE marking, b) creating a pilot production plant (including implementation of quality control and ensuring regulatory compliance) and securing a supply chain for components, c) implementation of a short-term plan where we sign up reference sites and that would be championed by key opinion leaders and d) the setting up of a strategic sales and marketing plan. The latter will involve the creation of a new spin-out to exploit commercial opportunities. A start-up using the novel AEGEUS technology will be able to capitalize itself to raising investment to generate new opportunities and careers.

Possible exploitation routes of the expected outputs:

- 1) A **proof-of-concept study** from the project forms the foundation to generating first-in-humandata and will also include evaluation of safety and analysis of critical risks. The exploitation of this data includes, beyond scientific publication, submission of data to the relevant authorities, specifically, to medical device agencies. This will eventually enable us to acquire CE marking.
- 2) A **full prototype** including an imaging and a stimulation module is expected to be an outcome of the project. Future exploitation could focus on a **scale-up** of the production with adherence to the new **EU MDR framework**. Development of the full prototype will be preceded by development work on an imaging only prototype. Laboratory reference sites (UNAK, CDK) and working with key opinion leaders will be utilised to prepare for this rolling-out.
- 3) A future exploitation consists also in the development of a strategic **sales and marketing plan**. This will mean the creation of a new spin-off where the novel AEGEUS technology can create investor interest and bring in highly technological and specialised jobs for skilled industrial researchers and managers. This will materialise after the lifetime of the project, as applicable. AKA will be central in contributing to this process with its long and successful experience of translating clinical products from bench to bedside during the last decade, e.g., point-of-care diagnostics and image-guided surgery probes. A new team would be recruited to identify new alliances, possible joint ventures, and sales forecasts.

Overall Settings Exploitation Plan

i) Glossary outlining the plan

To ensure successful exploitation, the consortium aims to engage in promotion of the technology at conferences and workshops and collaborate with industry leaders. By focusing on these key outputs and their respective exploitation models, it aims to maximise the impact and value of the developed neurotechnology. A well planned strategic approach will help us reaching our target customers effectively and contribute to the growth of the neurotechnology sector. With the first prototype, a novel ultrasound (US)-based functional imaging method will be used in conjunction with EEG, allowing for high spatiotemporal resolution monitoring of brain activity. Then, there follows the integration of US brain stimulation into the novel imaging device. The design of stimulation probes within the EEG cap and respective soft- and hardware will allow integration into the prototype. Patient safety will be documented using medical device reporting (MDR) structures that will include also a guide / manual for use of the device in-vivo. The EEG-US cap prototype will be studied in a significant sample of healthy volunteers (N=150) and patients with epilepsy (N=20).

ii) Underlying rationale

An unmet need of society is to develop deep brain stimulators (DBSs) that are non-invasive. The breakthrough of our project will allow sending signals by focused ultrasound in conjunction with EEG source reconstruction. This would be used to replace current standard of care surgical procedures by combining novel features of ultrasound-based stimulation such that high focality can be achieved. The high impact of our technology will be enhanced by using novel, data-driven reconstruction methods that will boost spatial and temporal resolution by combining two complementary modalities. The rationale of our proposal is based on the long-term vision that the non-invasive approach of DBS can substantially decrease healthcare costs and, as an effective treatment, reduce the necessity for full-time care. This long-term vision includes the aim to develop this new technology into a wearable headset that can incorporate dedicated stimulation patterns, and where frequency and intensity of the stimulation can be controlled by healthcare professionals, caretakers, or via self-application. The key technical challenges in the project involve ultrasound imaging and its combination with the EEG and stimulation techniques in the brain. The EEG-US brain stimulation capabilities that will complement the imaging device will be achieved by the design of stimulation probes within the EEG cap. Then, a proof of concept of EEG-US brain imaging and stimulation will allow us to gather first user experience, explore clinical needs and potential applications, document functions of the device and provide data about safety of its application.

iii) Alignment with the legal framework

The regulatory and legal frameworks guiding medical (neurological) devices onto the clinical market are fully considered and compliance with this framework is aligned with our goals. Our approach includes new methods of analysis and data visualisation to extract as much useful information as possible from non-invasive physiological recordings. Performance metrics to assess the safety and performance will be obtained systematically. Conventional ultrasound imaging of the brain is restricted to either thin skull sections or to open skull imaging during surgery, while the to-be developed device will be non-invasive and under the general category of a non-invasive medical device. Furthermore, to allow for a standalone application of both US imaging and stimulation, the device needs to infer the layout of ultrasound

transducers on a patient's skull without external reference. This is addressed in the design of dedicated novel data-driven calibration sequences of ultrasound signals that allow the device to infer the mutual position and orientation of the transducers on the skull. A major clinical question, however, is to understand the correlation between brain function and induced signal changes by transmitted or scattered ultrasound signals. A particular challenge is that the hardware of the imaging technique does not yet exist. Our approach will therefore need to involve simulations and phantom experiments in which i) several suspected physical effects are assessed for their detectability and ii) the difficulty of the experiment is increased by adding a skull model. Based on the detectability, hardware will be improved for clinical applicability. This will allow gathering the required clinical data. The innovative type of US and EEG data will allow for novel biophysical modelling and analysis of brain function. However, compliance with the EU MDR involves submission of many technical documents and we shall base development of these documents fully on the project demonstrating the safety and performance of the medical device. This paperwork will include an exhaustive overview of the device, its intended function, clinical evaluation, risk management, and plans for post-market surveillance. Moreover, we aim to prepare the build-up of a strong Quality Management System (QMS) that is in accordance with the norms and standards of the legislation.

Conducting meticulous clinical investigations to determine the safety and performance of medical devices will be an essential component for demonstrating our MDR compliance. To show that the device works in accordance with its intended use and is safe, clinical studies will be compiled, together with a systematic literature review. A new concept that the MDR has introduced is the unique identifier (UDI). This system increases traceability and post-market safety monitoring of individual medical devices. From now on, manufacturers must issue one unique identification number to each medical device they produce and enter that data in a UDI database. This allows for more efficient product recalls, more supply chain transparency, and easier reporting of adverse events. Ideally, one can use just the device number to locate the device. We also will consider MDR criteria when anticipating a future supply chain and verify that our suppliers and subcontractors meet EU MDR criteria. We will need to develop strong partnerships and quality agreements with suppliers in order to allow future control over the whole production process and guarantee the end product's quality and safety. Getting approved by the Notified Body is required for all higher-risk medical devices. These Notified Bodies are independent bodies (or professional organizations) appointed by EU member states to evaluate medical device compliance with the EU MDR. Before we can get a conformity certification for the product, we aim to have in place a procedure to working with a Notified Body based on experience, capability, and designation scope.

Procedures for Knowledge and IPR Management

Exploitation measures: Path to commercialisation

- 1) "Collect and Understand": Collect the respective application potential resulting from each WP using our internal "Knowledge Management Template", which will be completed by WP leaders to capture and describe the "Knowledge Outputs (KO)". This will i) capture the description of the KO, ii) focus on future users of each KO generated during the implementation, and iii) define future applications of the KO.
- 2) "Analyse and Validate": intellectual property rights (IPR) will be examined carefully, as this will influence any future knowledge transfer strategy. An essential element is the exact definition and analysis of relevant target groups (TGs), stakeholders and end users, the results of which will be captured in a Stakeholder Database. AKA has a record of interaction with patient organisations and doctors' associations and will enrich such database periodically. CDK hosts key players in the international league against epilepsy (ILAE) and is part of the European reference network (EPICare), which is an excellent starting point to gather neurological opinion leaders and patient organisations in the field of epilepsy.
- 3) "Exploitation and Dissemination Plans": These plans will be developed for individual or clusters of KOs depending on their type, IPR conditions, TG, or end-user target audiences. AKA will identify the most suitable channels and means for transferring the KOs to our TGs, which will ensure tailor-made transfer based on end-user focus in the EU. The exploitation phases of our KOs include the following: a) specification and design of the wearable head device in alignment with a blueprint so that the components may be integrated spatially with full functionality, b) hand production of an alpha prototype device, c) testing of the alpha prototype for ultrasound propagation through the skull, d) integration of ultrasound imaging with EEG in the device, e) hand production of the alpha plus prototype, f) optimisation of activity and comparison to state-of-the-art methods, g) proof of concept for ultrasound/EEG imaging, h) production of a beta prototype device for targeted neuromodulation/stimulation through the skull, i) regulatory testing, checks for compliance and risk assessment completed, j) preliminary studies in healthy human volunteers and patients with epilepsy to provide proof of principle in-vivo and to evaluate potential impact and usability in medical diagnostics and therapy, k) collection of data to show that this new imaging approach is able to provide functional information with high-spatial resolution, good depth of penetration and high focality

Management of IPR:

An innovation manager will be selected to manage IPR strategy. The rules to manage knowledge that was created during the project are clearly defined and managed in the CA. At the writing stage of the proposal, the participants have defined the following principles. First, our scope regarding the ownership of Background Knowledge will be to grant to the consortium partners responsible for the production of foreground knowledge all necessary access rights to the background knowledge required both for the implementation of the project and for the use of the foreground royalty-free. This will also be specified in the CA as follows: i) Access rights to the background knowledge (preexisting know-how) necessary for the implementation of the project during the term of the project will be made available to the Consortium members royalty-free. ii) Access to background knowledge for dissemination and academic purposes will be granted royalty-free to project partners. iii) IPRs of the background knowledge will be retained by the corresponding consortium partners after the end of the project. Second, ownership of Foreground

Knowledge. All participants can utilise it for future dissemination and academic purposes (royaltyfree), with commercial exploitation regulated by the CA and the Exploitation Plans. The following has been agreed upon: i) IPR of the foreground knowledge produced by consortium partners during the implementation of the project will be retained by the corresponding partners and divided proportionally, according to the effort invested in the production of the knowledge. Our innovation manager will keep internal knowledge management templates with input from all WP leaders. ii) Foreground knowledge will be made available on a royalty-free basis to all project partners for dissemination and academic purposes only, both during and after the project conclusion. iii) Project participants will retain the exploitation rights of corresponding project results ("foreground") for their intended use and will be granted access rights to utilise it on a royalty-free basis. Third, for the protection of foreground knowledge, it has been preliminarily agreed among project partners that the project results, which will be provided as open-source components, will be protected under open-source licenses while the project results that will be commercially exploited will be copyright-protected and will be provided on a licensing-based scheme.

Governance Model:

The development of a research and medical device to be applied to humans necessitates a multilevel governance framework to address the ethical, legal, and social implications of acquiring and processing brain data. The governance model for the AEGEUS project will be built on four key pillars: i) adherence to current binding regulations; ii) ethics; iii) responsible innovation and commercialisation and iv) human rights.

Regulations:

Brain data should be considered a special category of personal data that involves a unique type of collection and processing of information. It is crucial to adhere to current data protection regulations such as Article 9 of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) to ensure the privacy and security of individuals' brain data.

Ethics:

Established research ethics procedures, such as review through ethics committees and Institutional Review Boards (IRBs), are essential governance mechanisms for clinical neuroscience research. In addition, the AEGEUS project will work with scientific advisors that will provide additional guidance and address the novel challenges of harnessing the big-data ecosystem associated with brain data acquisition and processing.

Responsible Innovation and Commercialisation:

The project team will be considering innovation models and a business plan for our technology and neuromodulation at the end of the project. The team will also adopt community-agreed technical standards, validation, and deployment of best practices through a consensus process involving neurotechnology researchers, companies, and other stakeholders as needed or applicable.

Human Rights:

Access to brain data should be considered a universal right, ensuring that all individuals, regardless of ethnicity, gender, nationality, or religion, can benefit from advancements in neurotechnology and AI to improve their quality of life.

By incorporating a robust governance model based on these four pillars, the AEGEUS project will ensure the responsible development, implementation, and dissemination of its ground-breaking neurostimulation

technologies. This approach will help address the ethical, legal, and social challenges arising from the application of a medical device to humans while promoting the equitable distribution of benefits to individuals and society as a whole.

Knowledge and IPR state of play at AEGEUS

This is part of the consortium agreement.

Overview Dissemination Plan

The AEGEUS Dissemination Plan aims to raise awareness of the project's outputs among all relevant stakeholders. The primary objectives of the dissemination and outreach strategy are designed to increase innovation capacity within the Consortium. These objectives include:

- i) Ensuring effective communication and integration of new knowledge within the consortium, fostering regional and cross-border innovation clusters in Neurotech.
- ii) Disseminating AEGEUS research outputs and best practices both within and beyond the Consortium, while respecting the work of all partners.
- iii) Guaranteeing the visibility of the project's actions, outcomes, and activities supported by the project.
- iv) Encouraging sustainable cooperation and efficient knowledge exchange among various research and innovation entities within AEGEUS topics and interests.
- v) Promoting transparency in all adopted procedures while protecting confidential data (results/reports).

AKA will develop an initial version of the Dissemination Plan by the project's sixth month (m6) and present a revised plan at month 48 (m48).

Overall Dissemination Objectives

The AEGEUS consortium consists of a multidisciplinary team that aims to achieve the following objectives:

- i) Enhance scientific and technological expertise in phase separations, positioning Europe at the forefront of this field.
- ii) Provide high-quality training of human resources through a combination of training, mentoring, and dissemination activities.

To maximise the impact of its activities and strengthen collaboration among partners, AEGEUS will implement tools to optimise the effectiveness and reach of its dissemination, communication, and outreach activities. **The primary goals include:**

- i) Ensuring effective communication and equal dissemination of project goals and achievements among consortium participants.
- ii) Developing and maintaining dynamic social media communication.
- iii) Creating a unified communication toolkit and visual guidelines for AEGEUS consortium usage.
- iv) Disseminating the project's activities and outcomes to national and international scientific communities.
- v) Involving early-stage researchers (undergraduate, master, and Ph.D. students, lab technicians included) and junior postdocs in the project's activities.
- vi) Actively engaging with stakeholders throughout the project via targeted dissemination activities.
- vii) Laying the groundwork for the project's continuity.
- viii) Producing consultative and promotional materials for scientific awareness through dissemination via conventional public access routes or network-based systems.

The Dissemination Plan aims to unite all partners and participants in the communication process, thereby reinforcing the project's collaborative network and identity.

Target Groups (TG)

TG1: Industry, Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs) to expand our opportunities, activities targeting industry will primarily be aimed at discussing future exploitation and commercialisation opportunities extending beyond the project lifetime.

TG2: Scientific medical societies, academic researchers: The target device represents a novel generation of medical high-tech that has the potential to revolutionise joint diagnosis and treatment of brain disorders. Dialoguing with organisations that are experienced in comorbid pathological conditions, e.g., Epilepsy, Parkinson's disease and Alzheimer's disease, will serve as information multipliers since they usually organise large public communication events. Reaching out to clinical and patient organisations via the ILAE (international league against epilepsy) and associated associations will allow us to gather opinions from patients. Scientific dissemination at conferences for neurocognitive research will stimulate interest among the academic audience as a potential early adopter of the new technology for scientific purposes.

TG3: End-users, healthcare practitioners and clinicians: This group will help us in continuous interaction while designing and implementing our project results. Collecting systematically their first-hand knowledge of needs in neurological diseases is fundamental to identifying the patients for whom the project outcomes would be most beneficial. Key opinion leaders (KOLs) and clinicians will help to identify safety concerns, especially within the clinical environment.

TG4: Regulators for translations: AEGEUS envisages the organisation of meetings with regulatory authorities, where the consortium representatives from the participating companies (e.g., AKA) have been nominated to outline a strategy to communicate with the European Medicines Agency (EMA) and the Icelandic Medicines Agency (IMA). The regulatory bodies will be invited to two major events organised during the project lifetime.

TG5: Policymakers: The success of the project will not only form the basis for novel devices, which will ultimately improve health and QOL in otherwise difficult-to-treat diseases but also contribute to significantly reducing public health care costs both for patients and for caregivers. To this end, it is essential to closely interact with policymakers and governmental bodies to facilitate a smooth implementation of the project's wider outcomes in public health and community medicine strategies.

TG6: Citizens, families, general public, media: We will connect to national/local initiatives, media, and social media (Instagram, Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube, ResearchGate, Project Website, etc.) to inform the public about our research, findings, and technology.

Expected Research Findings to be disseminated

i) Types of data: Our output will be managed in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation [Regulation (EU) 2016/679]. The consortium will share its datasets contained in peer-reviewed publications while separately monitoring confidential data (e.g., patient data). Other data include digital imaging of the brain (NIFTI format) and evaluated data, the results, conclusions, reports or proof-of-concept runs (standard MS Office files).

ii) Findability: After adequate IP screening and data protection for privacy, the data will either be protected or made openly findable. Researchers can find the deposited data via persistent links from peer-reviewed publications or by searching the Materials Cloud Archive. Records of the Materials Cloud Archive are versioned, and a citable Direct Object Identifier (DOI) will be assigned to each record.

iii) Accessibility: our data will be openly available with as few restrictions as possible, with due diligence to protect sensitive data. All target groups will be able to access our open data by simply using their web browser. Where applicable, OpenAIRE's data anonymisation tool will be employed.

iv) Interoperability: We will use metadata vocabularies, standards, and methods to increase the interoperability of our data. Metadata will be stored internally in JSON (Java Script Object Notation) format in line with a defined JSON scheme.

v) Reusability: We will include additional information in our documentation to allow for its correct reuse by other researchers (README file, README tab, Data Dictionary, Codebook, Commented Code, Data Acquisition Protocols). For data that is accompanied by a license, a detailing permission associated with its use will be stored in their respective repository (i.e., in the README and metadata file).

vi) Curation and storage/preservation costs: The coordinator will nominate a DPO (Data Protection Officer) in charge of managing the data collected as follows: first, to design an automated process qualifying data and verifying integrity; second, to collect, archive and maintain patient consent; third, to define pseudonymisation to archive data for research. Our data will be stored and curated on a secure cloud certified to host personal data when necessary, e.g., to share data among partners. The cost to activate and maintain it for the duration of the project will be covered by the project budget.

Dissemination activities towards our Objectives and TGs

Corporate identity and visibility: We will create, design, and produce information and promotional material to define the visual identity of the project. These elements, like the already existing AGEUS logo, will be adopted in all presentations, reports, and posters as well as for meeting and internal documents in a Dissemination Toolkit. AKA will be responsible for the design and production of a set of standard dissemination materials, such as project leaflets and posters, which will be tailored to our TGs.

Public website: AEGEUS's website (<https://www.eic-aegeus.eu/>) is available and will be used as one of the main vehicles for dissemination and interaction with the target groups who are seeking information about our project. The website will be promoted through multiple channels (SEO, Social Media Marketing, Google). [all TGs, Quantified indicator: 3k unique visits to the project website, 2 news/month].

Social media: We will use social media for both communication and dissemination of the project and its results to an extremely wide and targeted audience and as a means of establishing our reputation. The main social media and communication channels that will be used are LinkedIn (to share content and connect with the healthcare community), Facebook/Instagram (Facebook page, associated Instagram), Twitter (share short comments and announcements that target audience can retweet), YouTube (videos providing project summaries and demonstrations of our novel technologies), or iTunes (for the planned podcasts to be distributed via RSS on Spotify/Google/Overcast, etc.). [all TGs, Quantified indicator: 500 followers on selected social media channels by the end of the project].

Press Releases: Our nonacademic consortium members (for example AKA) are already using press agencies such as Business Wire and the Press Association for press releases for their respective markets and communications, which will be one additional channel for quantifying the impact of our communication activities. [TGs 2-5, Quantified indicator: First by month 6, at least 3 by the end of the project].

EC services: Use of the services available from the EC (EC Research and Innovation Press Centre news alerts and newsletters, project stories for the EC newsroom, research*eu results and Horizon – The EU Research and Innovation Magazine) to spread awareness of AEGEUS and the role of EC funding. [all TGs, Quantified indicator: 1-2 releases per year].

Other Communication materials and activities: we will also use TV and radio programs for communicating to the public, audio-visual materials (short clips, animations, interviews, podcasts), digital material and newsletters (infographics for the general public, training materials), health focused portals (such as the Medical Device Developments), presentation material (for distribution in fairs, conferences and within partner's business/networking activities).

Additional public involvement: AEGEUS will involve the public throughout our research process and project implementation. Potential contributors or advisors will provide input to the design of the research questions, advise on the feasibility, and guide us towards additional channels to share our results. This will further be supported through the entire consortium and their organisations and extended network. [all TGs, Quantified indicator: To reach at least 8k people].

Envisaged networking: AEGEUS will use its extended network to establish or maintain collaborations with related projects and initiatives at the international, European and national/regional levels to share information and maximise the visibility of project results. [all TGs, Quantified indicators: 200 participants invited to our final conference].

Third-party events, National and international conferences and workshops, and Hands-on workshops: AEGEUS will build up interest by the scientific community by communicating the project plan and interim-results as well as final outcomes at scientific venues. Important conferences at which we will present ourselves are initially those that address US technology, explicitly IUS (<https://ieee-uffc.org/>) and ISTU (<https://istu.org/>), other technical conferences as EMBC (<https://embc.embs.org>) but also neuroscientific events such as the FENS forum (<https://fensforum.org/>) and OHBM (<https://www.humanbrainmapping.org>) and clinical conferences such as the annual conference of the ILAE (<https://www.ilae.org/congresses>) and the EAN (<https://www.ean.org/>).

Our activities will span throughout the lifespan of the project and beyond: i) Early in the project: We will set up our Exploitation and Dissemination Plan to establish systematic cooperation and exchange with our TGs. ii) During the project: We will run demo events to showcase the benefits of research and campaigns to understand human cognition and provide novel paradigms for treating brain diseases. We will also cluster with other ongoing projects (from within the consortium) to share knowledge. iii) Towards the end of the project: We will participate in third party events, scientific conferences and also organise workshops and a final conference to discuss the experiences gained through our project, foster mutual learning to exchange information on good practices, and run a policy roundtable to discuss relevant policy recommendations. iv) Beyond the end of the project: The entire consortium is committed to disseminating and exploiting project outcomes beyond its completion through their future activities and projects. Our defined TGs and

stakeholders that participated in our activities are expected to act as multipliers for the adoption of our outcomes.

List of consortium members' social media profiles

Partner	LinkedIn	Twitter or X	Facebook	Youtube
FM E	https://www.linkedin.com/company/franhofer-mevis/mycompany/	https://twitter.com/FranhoferMEVIS	no	no
IBMT	no	no	no	no
UR O M E	https://www.linkedin.com/school/sapienzauniversitadiroma/ https://www.linkedin.com/school/diagsapienza/	https://twitter.com/SapienzaRoma https://twitter.com/DIAGSapienza	https://www.facebook.com/SapienzaRoma https://www.facebook.com/DIAG.SAPIENZA/	https://www.youtube.com/@SapienzaRoma https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCbalD7wz_ATPrddPkYIVK1w
U N I T O V	https://www.linkedin.com/school/unitovergata/	https://twitter.com/unitovergata?lang=it	https://www.facebook.com/unitovergata/?locale=it_IT	https://www.youtube.com/c/Universit%C3%A0degliStudiDiRomaTorVergata
U N A K	https://www.linkedin.com/school/15095181/	https://twitter.com/HaskolinnAk	https://www.facebook.com/haskolinnaakureyri	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCUcKVXbvfDGS7UhniXNgq1g
G T E C	https://www.linkedin.com/company/gtec-medical-engineering/	https://twitter.com/gtec_BCI	https://www.facebook.com/gtec.at/	https://www.youtube.com/c/gtecmedicalengineering
C D K	https://at.linkedin.com/company/geminn%C3%BCtzige-salzburger-landeskliniken-betriebsges?trk=public	no	https://www.facebook.com/UniklinikumSalzburg	https://www.youtube.com/@uniklinikumsalzburg5510/featured
A K A	Not yet	https://twitter.com/akabiotech?s=11&t=X4zaKQ21jRGI5B7UJ4qclA	https://www.facebook.com/profile.php?id=100091532094379	no

List of consortium members' websites

Partner	website
FME	https://www.mevis.fraunhofer.de/
IBMT	https://www.ibmt.fraunhofer.de/ , http://www.ultrasound.fraunhofer.de/
UROME	https://www.uniroma1.it/en/
UNITOV	http://web.uniroma2.it/
UNAK	https://www.unak.is/english
GTEC	https://www.gtec.at/
CDK	https://salk.at/107.html , https://ccns.plus.ac.at/
AKA	https://akabiotech.info/

Key Performance Indicators

The success of the Dissemination Plan can be assessed using the following indicators:

- Level of acknowledgement of the project across Europe, focusing on two aspects: AEGEUS' primary stakeholders and the general public.
- Rates related to website and social media activities: Monitoring AEGEUS website traffic and analyzing the impact of events (e.g., publication of a new article) using web tools to provide comprehensive data on the number of visitors, pages visited, geographical coverage, and audience interests.
- Number of articles in non-scientific publications: The partner in charge will keep track of the number of publications.
- Number of external contact requests: A contact form on the AEGEUS website will enable external parties to reach the consortium. A specific form field will ask how they learned about AEGEUS and analyse the type of request to help determine the efficiency of communication and reinforce it in areas where more information requests are needed.
- Number of attendees at project events.

Impact assessment is an essential tool for ensuring the project objectives are being met through a selection of tailored activities. Evaluating the impact of communication activities can help understand the reach and sustainability of the project's results. Furthermore, the impact can be used to measure and assess promotional activities in terms of their relevance, quality, and chosen promotion channels.

Impact is often assessed using both quantitative and qualitative indicators for each activity or action. These (estimated) indicators are included in the table below:

INDICATOR	2023	2024	2025	2026	Source and methodology
Accumulated number of articles published					Registry of dissemination activities
Accumulated number of conferences and workshops					Registry of dissemination activities
Accumulated number of views of the video					YouTube registry
Accumulated number of subscribers to the project mailing list					Internal subscriber registry
Accumulated number of followers on LinkedIn					LinkedIn registry
Accumulated number of followers on Twitter					Twitter registry
Statistics					Stats Plug-in
Attendees of the events					Participation list

Risk Assessment

Risk for implementation	Level of Risk	Risk-mitigation measure
There is a gap between communication and the rest of the activities: partners are too focused on the specific WPs activities to get involved in communication, and tend to downplay obligations related to communications.	Medium	Each partner has to nominate a contact person in charge of communications. A core communication team is set up to coordinate communication efforts with a representative from each regional cluster.
Project results are too complex to be communicated. Partners tend to focus on their own objectives, and are not trained to identify effective messages to be communicated.	Medium	The communication leader and coleader will interact with the partners to identify the main messages. They will be encouraged to use the templates for an easier production. All products will be developed in cooperation with communication professionals.
Project fails to meet the target KPI values (number of participants during the events, social media engagement, number of post and articles, website traffic, etc.)	Low	In case of underperformance for a specific indicator, the communication team will devise a tailored plan with additional activities and measures to overcome these difficulties.
Lack of consistency of communications products (layout, language, etc.)	Low	Guidelines, quality control procedures and communications meetings will allow this risk to be overcome